

Thermal Analysis of the Flat Plate Collectors

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The use of solar dryer is slowly finding its way for food and other industrial drying in Nepal. Here in, we designed flat plate solar collector to make perfect black body by changing coating material on absorber metal plate with varied inclination of collector plate. The thermal performance analysis of a solar flat plate collector with black painting and selective coating has been carried out using outdoor test. The average thermal efficiency of black painted collector is 42.50% whereas for selective coated collector (67.62%) has more than existing collector. In order to supply the sufficient hot air from the collector to the chamber of heating application, the collector are installed at a slope of 45° and 37° facing south and operates in a closed loop mode with average inlet at 25°C to 38°C in Kathmandu valley with the ambient temperature of 24°C to 28°C. The in-depth analysis of this work may provide important guidance for the more rational design and optimization of solar dryer from the view point of collector.

Keywords: THERMAL EFFICIENCY, BLACK CHROME, COLLECTOR, SOLAR DRYER.

Introduction

Renewable energy technology is alternate of the global energy demand. It contributes to reduce dependency on finite conventional energy source like fossil fuels and other (reduce green house gases).The Kyoto protocol, which aims to reduce exhaust of greenhouse gases, has given incentive for many countries to rethink their energy policies.¹ Solar technologies are broadly characterized as either passive or active depending on the way they capture, convert and distribute sunlight. Active solar technique includes the uses of photovoltaic panels, solar thermal collector's with electrical or mechanical equipment, to convert sunlight into useful outputs. Passive solar techniques include orienting a building to the sun, selecting materials with favorable thermal mass or light dispersing properties, and designing spaces that naturally circulate air. These are applicable in energy conversion devices, central heating, cooking, drying and even refrigeration and so on.²The solar collector is a special kind of heat ex-changer that transforms solar radiant energy into heat. In this energy transfer is from distinct sources of radiant energy to fluid. The flux of incident radiation is at best, approximately $1100\text{W}/\text{m}^2$ with wavelength range of $0.3\mu\text{m}$ to $3\mu\text{m}$. The flat plat collector can be design for application requiring energy delivery at moderate temperature up to perhaps 100°C above ambient temperature.³ The electromagnetic radiation emitted by sun is from infrared UV wavelength and the energy that hit on the surface of the earth at normal condition is about 1000 watts per square meter.⁴

The flat plate collector forms the heart of any solar energy collector system and can be employed to heat fluid from ambient to near 100°C . The flat plate collectors are under investigation for the last 300 years. The reported flat plate collector was demonstrated by Mr. H.B. Saussure, a Swiss scientist during the second half of the seventeenth century. During the last six decades scientists in several countries mainly USA, UK, Australia, Israel, Germany, South Africa, China and India have built, tested, studied and optimized different types of flat plate collectors mainly liquid heating flat plate collectors.⁵ There are two methods for improving the performance of solar collectors: one is to increases solar flux incident on the absorber by using some type of concentrates and other is to reduction of heat loss from the absorbing surface. One of the most collectors used in practices is tubular which several advantages. They may be used to get the small concentration ration (1.5-2.0) by forming a mirror from part of the internal concave surface of a glass tube which focuses radiation on to the absorber inside the tube. Flat plat air heating collectors is conventional air heater is typically a flat passage between two parallel plates. One of the plates is blackened to absorb incident solar radiation. One or more transparent covers are located above the absorbing surface. Insulation around the sides and base pf the unit is necessary to keep heat losses to a minimum. Because of Airflow, Absorber plate material, Natural convection barriers and plate to air heat transfer coefficient, crumpled or corrugated sheets and wire screens are attractive as absorbing material. Insulation is required at the absorber

bases to minimize heat losses through the underside of the heater. Solar radiation data corresponding to the site are needed to evaluate heater performance.⁶

The factors affecting the performance of flat plate collector are solar radiation, temperature, relative humidity, air-flow rate, insulation, coating materials etc. On the basis of the structure solar collector are classified as flat plate collector and concentrating collector. This type of collector is used to produce more temperature for solar drying system which are quite complicated to analysis and are used in device live solar cooker. Research and development works on different types of solar dryers have been done since 1790's in our country. Among various types of solar dryers available in the world, mostly three types are used in our country namely; cabinet, rack and tunnel are used for different purposed. In our country cabinet is used in mustang, Ayurvedic association in Banepa, Kavrepalanchoke for drying herbal plants, while rack is used in department of Herbarium at Godawar, Herbarium farm at Manichaur near Sankhu and at Tistung, at Marpha, Sabai International Pv. Ltd in Kathmandu, Bhairahawa fabricated for ginger drying. Also tunnel is used in marpha in mustang, at Women self help group, Thankot Mahila Samuha in Kathmandu; Kailasnagar, Chitwanand Biratnagar, Morang.⁷⁻⁹

In 2016 Our group design the indirect Solar dryer has theoretical efficiency 27.05% which is increased by 2.42% in comparison to previous design.¹⁰ While doing performance evaluation using 10kg of cauliflower the maximum efficiency was 30.14%.¹¹ These all dryer has flat plate collector with carbon black painting so now we designed flat plate solar collector to make perfect black body by changing coating material on absorber metal plate with varied inclination of collector plate. The thermal performance analysis of a solar flat plate collector with black painting and selective coating has been carried out using outdoor test.

Materials and methods

For the improvement of existing flat plate collector, we have taken standard test procedure equations which are mention below in mathematical model to test thermal efficiency of collector. We measured various parameters, collector plate temperature, ambient temperature and coating material to estimating the contributing towards efficiency. Furthermore, we have fitted efficiency plots for both black painted collector and self-designed selective coating collector on the basis of measured parameters to compare their efficiency and graphical analysis was carried out to conclude our outcomes.

Mathematical Model for Thermal Performance Prediction: The amount of heat gain or heat collection rate of the collector is

$$Q = AI(\tau\alpha) - Q_L = A [I(\tau\alpha - U_L(T_p - T_a))]$$

Where A is of absorber plate, $(\tau\alpha)$ is transmittance absorption product, U_L is overall loss coefficient, T_p is mean absorber plate temperature and T_a is ambient temperature.

On solving we get

$$Q = h_w A (T_p - T_{fm})$$

where T_{fm} is mean air in the air heater duct.¹²

Now the energy from the outer surface of glass cover, the heat is rejected by radiation to the sky at temperature T_s and convection to the ambient air therefore

$$Q_{tgo} = A [\sigma \epsilon_g (T_{go}^4 - T_s^4) + h_w (T_{go} - T_a)]$$

where T_{go} is temperature of outer surface of glass cover.

In equilibrium condition heat transfer from absorber plate at T_p to inner surface of glass cover =

Heat transfer through the glass cover of thick certain thickness = heat rejected by radiation to the sky at certain temperature and convection to ambient air.¹³

The absorber plate inner surface and duct bottom surface long wave emissivity values ϵ_{pi} , ϵ_b and have been assumed to be 0.9. The heat balance for black surface gives heat transfer by radiation from the heat absorber plate to the duct bottom surface is equal to heat edge bottom surface at the temperature transfers heat to surrounding through back insulation and air flow through duct at meantemperature.¹²

Energy Balance Equation for Flat Plate Collector:

For a flat plate collector of area the energy balance equation can be written as

$$Q_a = I_{\tau\alpha} (T\alpha)e$$

Where $(T\alpha)e$ = effective transmittance - absorptance product.

Under steady state condition, the heat balance of absorber is gives: useful heat collected = heat absorbed by plate - heat losses is given by

$$q_u = I_{\tau\alpha} (T\alpha)e - U_L (T_p - T_a)$$

Replacing T_p by T_i and multiply whole right side by F_R (Heat removal efficiency factor) equation gives

$$q_u = F_R [I_{\tau\alpha} (T\alpha)e - U_L (T_i - T_a)]$$

Now the instantaneous efficiency of collector η_c is define simply as the ration of useful energy derived to the total solar energy falling on collectors

$$\eta_c = \frac{q_u}{A_c I_{Tt}}$$

Now, the efficiency over finite time period can express as

$$\eta_c = \frac{\int_0^t q_u}{\int_0^t A_c I_{Tt}}$$

Also

$$\eta_c = \frac{Q_u}{A_c I_{Tt}} = F_R \left[(\tau\alpha) e^{-\frac{U_L}{A_c I_{Tt}} (T_i - T_a)} \right]$$

$$\eta_c = \frac{m^o C_p (T_i - T_a)}{A_c I_{Tt}}$$

Since, $Q_u = m^o C_p (T_i - T_a)$

These equations are the basis of the standard test procedure. The general test procedure is to operate the collector in the test facility under nearly steady condition, measure the data to determine Q_u from the equation and measure I_{Tt} , and T_a which are needed for analysis based on the equation of necessity, this means outdoor tests are done in the midday hours on clear days when the beam radiation is high and usually with the beam radiation nearly normal to the collector.

Thus the transmittance-absorbance product for these test conditions is approximately then normal test are made with a range of inlet temperature conditions. To minimize effects of heat capacity of collectors, tests are usually made in nearly symmetrically pairs, one before and one after solar noon, with results of the pairs, averaged. Instantaneous efficiencies are determined from the equation of the averaged pairs, and are plotted as a function of $(T_i - T_a)/I_{Tt}$. If U_L , F_R , and $(\tau\alpha)_n$ were all constant, the plots of η_i versus $(T_i - T_a)/I_{Tt}$ would be a straight line with intercept $F_R(\tau\alpha)_n$ and slope $F_R U_L$.^{12,14}

We know that U_L is the function of temperature and wind speed, with decreasing dependence as the number of covers increases. Also, F_R is a weak function of temperature and some variations of the relative proportions of beam, diffuse, and ground-reflected components of solar radiation will occur. Thus scatter in the data are to be expected, because of temperature dependence, wind effect and angle of incidence variations. In spite of these difficulties, long time performance estimates of many solar heating systems, collectors can be characterized by intercept and slope as mentioned above.

Collector Instantaneous Efficiency of Black Painted Collectors

Table 1: Non Selective coated flat plate collectors

Overall Dimension	1.75m×1m×0.33m
Effective Length	1.75m
Effective Breath	0.85m
Effective Area	1.49m ²
Area of inlet	0.0288m ²
Collector Inclination	37 Degree
Absorber metal	Aluminum Plate
Glazing	Black Painting
Air Convection	Forced Type
Insulation	Styrofoam
Glass Cover	Ordinary

The collectors' instantaneous efficiency for black painted collector is given by

$$\eta_c = \frac{m^{\circ} c_p (T_0 - T_i)}{A_c I_{Tt}}$$

Since, Specific heat capacity of air at T_a is $C_p = 1.005 \times 10^3 / \text{KgK}$, Where m° is rate of flow of mass then above equation become

$$\eta_c = \frac{38.98}{I_{Tt}} (T_0 - T_i)$$

Where, I_{Tt} = Instantaneous solar radiation falling on absorber plate, T_0 = Outlet air temperature and T_i = Inlet air temperature.

Collector Instantaneous Efficiency of Selective Coating

Table 2: Non Selective coated flat plate collectors.

Overall Dimension	2m×1m×0.2m
Effective Length	1.9m
Effective Breath	0.9m
Effective Area	1.71m ²
Area of inlet	0.0288m ²
Collector Inclination	45 Degree
Absorber metal	Aluminum Plate
Glazing	Black chrome
Air Convention	Forced Type
Insulation	Styrofoam
	Sun glass containing
Glass Cover	low iron

The collectors' instantaneous efficiency for black chrome selective coating collector is given by

$$\eta_c = \frac{m^{\circ} c_p (T_0 - T_i)}{A_c I_{Tt}}$$

Since, Specific heat capacity of air at T_a is $C_p = 1.005 \times 10^3 / \text{KgK}$, where m° is rate of flow of mass then above equation become $\eta_c = \frac{33.97}{I_{Tt}} (T_0 - T_i)$

Where, I_{Tt} = Instantaneous solar radiation falling on absorber plate, T_0 = Outlet air temperature and T_i = Inlet air temperature.

Result and Discussion

In this experiment thermal instantaneous efficiency calculated from above equation for black paint absorber plate collector and selective coating black chrome on absorber flat plate solar collector. The Instantaneous thermal efficiency (η_i) as ordinates and temperature factor $(T_i - T_a) / I_{Tt}$ as abscissa to analysis of the efficiency factor and loss coefficient. During the measurement the average plate temperature are also noticed for both collectors with respect to time, to know effective performance requires dry atmosphere for better dryer so relative humidity plays an important role that's relative humidity data are also noticed using wet and dry bulb hygrometer where experiments were conducted.

Experiment on Black Painted Collectors: we plotted graph between thermal instantaneous efficiency as ordinates and abscissa to analysis of efficiency factor and loss coefficient. We used mathematica.9 program to plot graph. From the plot mention below, we found that product of efficiency factor, absorbance and transmittance factor are approx. 0.47046. Furthermore, the product of loss coefficient and efficiency factor is found to be approx. 11.4397W/m²c. These data were obtained from experiment which is plot in figure 1 below. The average instantaneous thermal efficiency from the experiment is approx.42.50%.

Figure 1: Temperature factors vs efficiency experiment on black painted collectors with best fit.

Experiment on Selective Coated Collectors: The average instantaneous thermal efficiency in this experiment is 67.62% and the product of efficiency factor and absorptance and transmittance factor is 0.685393from the plot. As a result product of loss coefficient and efficiency factor is 14.3581w/m²c.

Figure 2: Temperature factors vs efficiency experiment on selective coated collectors with best fit.

Conclusion

We have performed two set of experiments for flat plate collectors. The average thermal efficiency of black painted collectors is found 42.50% and for black chrome selective coated collectors is 67.62%. The thermal performance analysis of solar air heater flat plate collector with selective coating and black painting has been carried out using outdoor test with mathematical model best fit is done. The collector is installed at slope of 45° and 37° facing south and operates in a closed loop mode with inlet air at 25°C to temperature 38°C in Kathmandu Valley. The ambient temperature has been varied from 24°C to 28°C . The efficiency of black painted collector is 25.12% less than selective chrome coated collectors and average temperature obtained by selective chrome coat is 5°C greater than black painted collectors.

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